

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The article considers the relevance of learning English in the modern world. Students' ideas about the importance of learning English, the profession of an English teacher, including the prospects for the professional life of teachers in this specialty, are described.

Key words: language, scientific, foreign language, second language, translation, imagine

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается актуальность изучения английского языка в современном мире. Описаны представления студентов о важности изучения английского языка, профессии учителя английского языка, в том числе о перспективах профессиональной жизни учителей этой специальности.

Ключевые слова: язык, научный, иностранный язык, второй язык, перевод, представить

Annotatsiya: Maqolada zamonaviy dunyoda ingliz tilini o'rganishning dolzarbligi muhokama qilinadi. Talabarning ingliz tilini o'rganishning ahamiyati, ingliz tili o'qituvchisi kasbi, shu jumladan, ushbu mutaxassislik bo'yicha o'qituvchilarning kasbiy hayotining istiqbollari haqidagi fikrlari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: til, ilmiy, xorijiy til, ikkinchi til, tarjima, tasavvur qilmoq

“Those who know many languages lives as the language they know”

“You can never understand one language until understand at least two”

-Geoffrey Willans

Foreign languages are absolutely necessary for people nowadays. It is known that today international contacts with foreign countries are growing. There are over 7000 languages in the world. It means that there are many reasons for studying them.

For example, some people study a foreign language to communicate with people from another countries, other study it for having a good career in future. Learning this or that language we are planning to travel to the country where it is spoken, we try to communicate with native speakers and understand what they are saying to us. If we are working in any branch of science, we naturally wish to read scientific books and magazines in other languages to rise our

professional level. Making business nowadays also depends on knowing foreign languages. The ability of speaking one or more foreign language helps people from different countries over the world to develop friendship and understanding. People can also make intellectual and cultural horizons wider through contacts with people of another culture: We really like reading foreign literature in its original form, we can also read foreign newspapers and magazines watch films listen to music without any help and translation. In many cultures attempting to speak foreign language is viewed as a sign of respect and has the potential to open doors for the future. One of the most reasons of learning foreign language is making your brain work all time; it gives you a greater global understanding of the world we live in. But learning a new language takes time and dedication. Being a student of the University of Foreign Languages we know advantages of learning foreign languages. As we study English here, we will try to show you the importance of learning English language.

English is a universal language and it is spoken in many countries in the world. English is the official language of 45 countries. It is spoken by around four hundred million people. That's why we can say that English is the most widely used language in the world. A lot of people cannot imagine their life without studying English. In order to sound educated and literate people need to thoroughly study English. It is also heavily needed in business world as well as your own private world. English also teaches us to communicate and process things more accurately. If we did not have a set English language communicating would be extremely difficult.

The main reason to study English is to sound educated and literate. In order to advance in the professional world, you must have proper English and good speech. in additional reason for studying English is for communication. We are much more accepted in the world if we portray ourselves better. People will think about us in a better way and we will have a chance of being accepted. We will have more opportunities in life.

We are sure every well-educated person should speak English because it is the language of communication, business, science and culture. English is now very important and widespread language in the world because it is the state language in five countries: Great Britain, Canada, Australia, America and New Zealand. Nowadays a lot of people study foreign languages in every possible way. Many people think that English is worth studying. There is proverb "A new language-a new world." It is known that learning English opens up a world of new

opportunities. For example, people who know English perfectly can travel practically anywhere in the world. They do not have any troubles with translations. Everything is clear for them. Such kind of people can go about their business and in other countries and speak freely to locals and other travellers. They will have a much better experience as these people can effectively communicate with much more people, which will ultimately open up their mind and put things into different perspectives regarding the different cultures of the world.

Learning English as a second language focuses our attention on the grammatical rule's constructions of that language. This experience gives people a new insight into their own and language ultimately leads to them improving their mother tongue, which will improve their everyday lives. Learning English is an achievement everyone can be proud of and is extremely satisfying. English helps us to get a job. This popular language can help you to recognize many interesting things. For example: customs and traditions, literature and folk, style and culture, history and economy. English is very important for career advancement and respect in the business world. Learning English never ends. There is the English dictionary that has so many words in it that most people have never seen or heard.

Based from. All the above elaboration, we hope that reader will see the importance of learning foreign languages. How this important language will help us in our future.

Although it is the second language in our country, it is main language all over the world

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